

Sociodemographic and contextual variables as predictors of men's health insurance enrolment in Ghana: Evidence from a micro indicator cluster survey

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Abstract

Introduction: This study explores the ability of sociodemographic and contextual variables, including ethnicity, rural/urban residence, and region, to predict health insurance enrollment among men in Ghana.

Methods: This study employs primary data from the Ghana Micro Indicator Cluster Survey (MICS) 2017/2018. The compositional and contextual variables were tested as the main predictors of health insurance coverage in two multivariable ordinal logistic models using odd ratios and p-values after Spearman's rho correlation analysis was conducted.

Results: Spearman's rho correlation analysis revealed a positive relationship between age and health insurance coverage and a similar relationship between rural/urban residence and health insurance coverage. Educational level and wealth index quintile were the most significant predictors of health insurance coverage among men in Model 1. Including ethnicity, rural/urban area of residence, and regional location as contextual factors in Model 2 revealed an improved effect of the existing sociodemographic variables except for functional difficulty, which was not statistically significant.

Discussion: Low health insurance coverage among men can increase vulnerabilities and gendered tendencies associated with enrolment in health insurance services. The sociodemographic and geo-related context-specific variations depict the differential effects in the predictors of men's health insurance coverage.

Take-home message: Low-income countries must consider the segmentation and targeting of diverse population groups at the micro level and critically examine the sociodemographic and locational dynamics that can influence their acceptance and subscription to ex-ante coping mechanisms that can mitigate the financial burden related to healthcare costs and at the same time enhance strategies put forward to promote universal healthcare coverage.

Keywords: health insurance; men's health; health disparities; Ghana.

INTRODUCTION

Health insurance enrolment is a major platform for accessing and utilizing healthcare services in developing countries as they strive towards universal health coverage [1]. However, there are disparities in the enrolment rate due to compositional and contextual factors [2]. Gendered patterns of healthcare services utilization within urban and rural contexts, income and wealth quintiles, and effects emanating from educational levels and cognitive factors tend to influence enrolment at the individual level; health insurance enrolment among men in Ghana remains relatively low. The seemingly patriarchy tendencies in most developing countries and power dynamics among men usually facilitate the neglect of critical academic inquiry into ex-ante coping strategies employed to address their healthcare needs. In the case of Ghana, the existence of a voluntary national health insurance scheme and the volition to freely enroll in any privately regulated health insurance scheme leave the choice of enrolment in the will of individuals and adult household members, where men tend to be the major decision-makers [3]. Enshrined in the national health insurance scheme based on the National Health Insurance (NHIS) Act 2012 (Act 852) is an insurance premium component that denies the automatic enrolment of all people resident in Ghana regardless of the pluralistic fund mobilization strategies in the scheme [4-6]. Hence, individuals are likely influenced by sociodemographic and locational factors [7,8]. It has been argued that to achieve equity and the pro-poor objectives in the Ghana health insurance system, it is necessary to understand the issues design and implement such interventions appropriately [9].

Further, it has been expressed that the absence of compulsory insurance enrolment, annual enrolment and renewal arrangements, and the discretionary determination of exempted groups apart from Livelihood Empowerment Against Poverty (LEAP) beneficiaries tend to serve as barriers to enrolment [9,18,19]. Central in the literature on health insurance enrolment has been the arguments on quality of care, facility, adequacy of benefit packages, price, and convenience [1]. However, delving deeper is the potential of selected geo-demographic elements that directly and indirectly influence the perception factors. This study explores the predictive ability of sociodemographic elements such as age, education level, income level, and geo-referenced variables such as ethnicity, rural/urban residence, and region as predictors of NHIS enrolment. Thus, this study explores the predictive effects of selected categorical variables in two ordinal logistic models using data from a micro-indicator cluster study in Ghana.

METHODS

This study uses primary data from the Ghana Micro Indicator Cluster Survey (MICS) 2017/2018 to analyze the relationship between selected sociodemographic and locational variables and health insurance enrolment among men aged 15-49 years in Ghana. The data sources, variables measured, and analyses have been presented.

To provide estimates for many indicators on the situation of diverse demographic groups at the national level, rural and urban areas, and existing administrative regions, the Ghana Statistical Service undertook a micro indicator cluster survey (MICS) in 2017/2018. A multi-stage sampling frame was used to classify urban and rural areas in each region as the significant sampling strata. Subsequently, it employed a two-stage approach in selecting households established in basic enumeration units by the 2010 population and housing census. A systematic sampling approach determined 20 households in each enumeration unit where survey questionnaires were administered. Specifically, this study employed the questionnaire for individual men in every second household to all men aged 15-49 years. In all, 5,476 were eligible for the survey. However, 5,323, representing 97.2%, took part in the survey. Further, establishing ordinal logistics resulted in using responses from 4,309 respondents after excluding missing responses.

Measured items and analysis

This study used items on the men's background, marriage/union, and adult functioning. The dependent variable, health insurance enrolment, was denoted by health insurance coverage. The independent variables were age group, men's

educational level, marital status, wealth index quintile, and functional difficulty, which served as compositional attributes tested in Model 1. The constructs on ethnicity, urban and rural residence, and geographic region were added as the contextual factors in Model 2.

The enumerated compositional and contextual variables were tested as the main predictive factors of health insurance coverage in two multivariable ordinal logistic models based on existing and established statistical benchmarks. The models employed the use of odd ratio (OR) and p-values to interpret the relationship in the categories of the measured items, which were not held to be redundant in the model. The models were established after an item correlation analysis using Spearman's rho correlation since the measured items were binary and categorical. The acquisition of significant correlation values was based on Spearman's rho correlation values and statistically significant values of either $p < 0.001$ or < 0.005 . In establishing model goodness of fit, the deviance/df of 1.255 and chi-square/df of 1.050 were analyzed with the omnibus test results of $p < 0.001$. The results section presents the descriptive outcome and the co-efficient in regression analysis.

Ethical aspects

UNICEF and the Ghana Statistical Service obtained verbal consent from each respondent participating. The right to use the data was granted to the Author by the Ghana Statistical Service after approval of the data request protocols. The standard guidelines can be found at <http://mics.unicef.org/tools#data-processing>.

RESULTS

The findings from the study are subsequently discussed. The descriptive dimension involves an analysis of the frequency and percentage variables used for the research. In all, a total of 4,309 respondent men between the ages of 15 to 49 years who participated in the study were used in the analysis.

The frequency from the dependent variable, which is health insurance coverage, showed that 1,764 (40.9%) respondents had valid health insurance (HI) coverage, whereas 2,545 (59.1%) did not have health insurance coverage. Regarding age categorization, the ages between 15 and 24 constituted 1,410 (32.7%), whereas the oldest age category of 44 to 49 years constituted 534 (12.4%). Further, the age data showed a gradual decline in respondents based on age progression, which is coterminous with the national population pyramid. The categorical variable on men's education level showed that 659 (15.3%) had pre-primary or no formal education, whereas primary and junior secondary/middle school constituted 538 (12.4%) and 1,414 (32.8%), respectively. Further, senior secondary and tertiary or higher education included 1,181 (27.4%) and 517 (12%), respectively. The identification of men in marital unions showed that 2,415 (56%) were in marital unions at the time of the survey, whereas 161 (3.7%) of the respondents had formerly been married. Moreover, 1,733 (40.2%) of the men had never married or been in union.

Table 1. Frequency distribution of sociodemographic variables.

Variable	Measured Item	N	Percent (%)
Covered by health insurance	Yes	176	40.9%
		4	
	No	254	59.1%
		5	
	Total	430	100.0%
		9	
Age Group	15 to 24 years	141	32.7%
		0	

	25 to 34 years	128	29.8%
		5	
	35 to 44 years	108	25.1%
		0	
	44 to 49 years	534	12.4%
	Total	430	100.0%
		9	
Man's Education	Pre-primary or none	659	15.3%
	Primary	538	12.5%
	JSS/JHS/Middle	141	32.8%
		4	
	SSS/SHS/ Secondary	118	27.4%
		1	
	Higher	517	12.0%
	Total	430	100.0%
		9	
Marital/Union status of man	Currently married/in union	241	56.0%
		5	
	Formerly married/in union	161	3.7%
	Never married/in a union	173	40.2%
		3	
	Total	430	100.0%
		9	
Wealth index quintile	Poorest	109	25.3%
		0	
	Second	677	15.7%
	Middle	732	17.0%
	Fourth	811	18.8%
	Richest	999	23.2%
	Total	430	100.0%
		9	
Functional difficulties (age 18-49 years)	Has functional difficulty	231	5.4%
	Has no functional difficulty	407	94.6%
		8	
	Total	430	100.0%
		9	
Ethnicity of household head	Akan	157	36.6%
		8	
	GA/Damgme	307	7.1%
	Ewe	538	12.5%
	Guan	148	3.4%

	Gruma	174	4.0%
	Mole Dagbani	102	23.7%
		2	
	Grusi	190	4.4%
	Mande	15	0.3%
	Other	335	7.8%
	Missing	2	0.0%
	Total	430	100.0%
		9	
Area	Urban	195	45.3%
		0	
	Rural	235	54.7%
		9	
	Total	430	100.0%
		9	
Region	Western	433	10.0%
	Central	338	7.8%
	Greater Accra	537	12.5%
	Volta	372	8.6%
	Eastern	405	9.4%
	Ashanti	560	13.0%
	Brong Ahafo	379	8.8%
	Northern	467	10.8%
	Upper East	378	8.8%
	Upper West	440	10.2%
	Total	430	100.0%
		9	

Note: Pre-primary or none: Pre-primary school or none; Primary: Primary School; JSS/JHS/Middle: Junior Secondary School; SSS/SHS/ Secondary Higher: Senior Secondary School Higher; Tertiary Education.

The parameter on wealth quintile, ascribed in literature as influencing the ability to pay for health insurance coverage, depicted that 1,090 (25.8%) of the respondents were in the poorest wealth quintile. The second and middle wealth index quintile constitute 677 (15.7%) and 732 (17%). 811 (18.8%) and 999 (23.2%) respondents were in the fourth and richest wealth index quintiles. The inclusive objectives of health insurance programs necessitated the examination of functional difficulty as part of the independent variables. It was observed that 231 (5.4%) of the respondents had functional problems. The descriptive statistics on the ethnicity of male household heads in the study were also obtained. Further, the area was represented by 1,950 (45.3%) and 2,359 (59.7%) of respondents living in rural and urban areas respectively. The regional data revealed that Greater Accra and Ashanti had relatively higher respondent numbers of 537 (12.5%) and 560 (13%).

Further, descriptive analysis was conducted among all the 5,476 respondents surveyed on the type of health insurance coverage before proceeding with inferential statistics on 4,309 respondents generated after the excluded cases. National

health insurance coverage constituted 2,266 (41.4%), whereas health insurance through an employer constituted 20 (0.4%). Other privately purchased commercial health insurance were 14 (0.3%).

Figure 1. Reasons for non-enrolment of health insurance among men.

More importantly, the individual reasons why some respondents never registered with private insurance or NHIS were analyzed. From the survey, respondents who felt premiums were too high were 108 (2%), whereas lack of confidence in health insurance scheme operation was 82 (1.5%). The absence of knowledge of any health insurance scheme constituted 23 (0.4%), while the lack of understanding of where to register was 22 (0.4%). Other views on long distances of registration were 111 (2.1%), whereas 285 (5.2%) of the respondents did not find a need for health insurance. Further reasons include limited service or facility coverage, which constituted 58 (1.1%), and no money for enrollment, indicated by 509 (9.3%) of the respondents.

The findings from the demographic variables and subsequent observations made from the reasons assigned by respondents necessitate an examination of the effect of the antecedent compositional and contextual variables on the dependent variable of health insurance cover by first establishing a Spearman rho correlation due to the presence of binary and categorical data type and secondly ascertain the levels of effect through two multivariable ordinal logistic regression models after the goodness of fit indices have been demonstrated. The correlation results showed that age group and rural/urban residence, herein referred to as area, positively correlated with health insurance coverage, as shown by correlation values of 0.044 and 0.110 at $p < 0.001$, respectively.

Table 2. Spearman's rho correlation analysis.

	Covered by HI	Age group	Man's Education	Marital status	WIQ Functional Status (18-49 years)	Ethnicity Household head	Area	Region
Covered by HI	1.000							
Age group	.044**	1.000						

Men's Education	-.168**	-.120**	1.000						
Marital status	-.066**	-.767**	.187**	1.000					
WIQ	-.127**	.075**	.543**	.014	1.000				
Functional Status (18-49 years)	-.035*	-.053**	.085**	.036*	.085**	1.000			
Ethnicity of Household head	-.054**	-.004	-.280**	-.027	-.383*	-.002	1.000		
Area	.110**	-.023	-.373**	-.060*	-.583*	-.063**	.200**	1.0	
Region	-.151**	-.034*	-.258**	.007	-.422*	-.021	.582**	.25	1.000

Note: HI: Health Insurance * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed) ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Though most of the independent variables negatively correlated with health insurance coverage, there was a solid inter-item correlation among some of the independent variables. The primary objective of employing ordinal logistic regression models to ascertain the effects led to the setting up of two models made up of social demographic variables serving as the predictors of health insurance cover in model 1 and the subsequent establishment of an interactive model made up of both sociodemographic and contextual factors serving as predictors of health insurance cover in model 2. The goodness of fit indicators showed a deviance value/df of 1.255 and a chi-square value/df of 1.050. The omnibus test showed a significant value of $p < 0.001$. In the model effect, only functional difficulty (disability) did not have a statistically significant effect, as demonstrated by $p = 0.771$; the remaining independent variables had significant $p < 0.001$ or $p < 0.005$.

Ordinal logistic regression results

The results from Model 1, which analyzed the effects of age group, education level, marital status, wealth index quintile, and functional difficulty as the main sociodemographic factors influencing health insurance coverage, revealed the existence of relationships. Within the age parameters, while holding the oldest category of 44 to 49 years redundant, respondents aged 15 to 24 had an odd ratio of 1.127 with a lower bound Wald interval of 0.863 and upper bound of 1.473. Progressively, ages 25 to 35 saw an odd ratio of 1.437 with a p-value of 0.002. The ages between 35 and 44 years saw an odd ratio of 1.066 with a lower bound of 0.857 and an upper bound of 1.325. Men's education level showed a relatively higher effect on health insurance coverage as signified by odd ratios 2.943, 3.914, 3.201, and 2.030, all at $p < 0.001$ for Pre-Primary, Primary, JHS, and SHS levels, respectively. The responses under marital status also demonstrated the existence of a positive odd ratio of 1.043 and 1.856, with the latter being those formerly married having a significant statistical value of 0.002.

Further, all elements under the wealth index quintile coincided with health insurance coverage, with only the poorest category showing a relatively lower odd ratio of 1.453 with $p < 0.005$. The remaining quintiles showed a higher odd ratio and $p < 0.001$. However, although the element of functional difficulty had an odd ratio of 1.081, it did not have a statistically significant value. The lack of finality in the effects of the demographic variables on the dependent variable augments the inclusion of contextual variables *sin quo non*, hence the establishment of Model 2.

The findings from Model 2 reveal a slight progressive effect of the age variables. Similarly, men's education level continues to be a key determinant of health insurance coverage with an improved add ratio, with the highest having a 3.932 odd ratio with $p < 0.001$. Marital status had a relatively lower odd ratio in Model 2 than in Model 1. However, there was a significant improvement in the effects of the parameters under the wealth index, as shown by the observance of higher odd ratios ranging from 2.659 to 1.684, all at $p < 0.001$. In Model 2, it was still observed that though functional difficulty had an odd ratio of 0.956, it did not have a statistically significant value.

Table 3. Ordinal logistic regression model.

Parameter		Model 1				Model 2				
Estimates		Exp(B)	95% Wald Confidence		p-value	Exp(B)	95% Wald Confidence		p-value	
Parameter			Interval for Exp(B)				Interval for Exp(B)			
			Lower	Upper			Lower	Upper		
Age Group										
15 To 24 Years		1.127	.863	1.473	.380	1.112	.841	1.470	.456	
25 To 34 Years		1.437	1.148	1.799	.002	1.463	1.158	1.848	.001	
35 To 44 Years		1.066	.857	1.325	.565	1.090	.870	1.367	.454	
44 To 49 Years		1	.	.	.	1	.	.	.	
Education Level										
Pre-Primary	Or	2.943	2.208	3.921	.000	3.458	2.551	4.687	.000	
None										
Primary		3.914	2.931	5.227	.000	3.932	2.905	5.321	.000	
JSS/JHS/Middle		3.201	2.541	4.033	.000	2.647	2.079	3.372	.000	
SSS/SHS/		2.030	1.619	2.546	.000	1.907	1.506	2.413	.000	
Secondary										
Higher		1	.	.	.	1	.	.	.	
Marital Status										
Currently		1.043	.862	1.263	.664	.965	.790	1.179	.729	
Married/In Union										
Formerly		1.856	1.253	2.750	.002	1.557	1.033	2.348	.035	
Married/In Union										
Never	Married/In	1	.	.	.	1	.	.	.	
Union										
Wealth Index										
Poorest		1.453	1.173	1.800	.001	2.659	1.996	3.542	.000	
Second		1.879	1.502	2.350	.000	2.534	1.926	3.334	.000	
Middle		1.738	1.406	2.148	.000	2.007	1.583	2.545	.000	
Fourth		1.523	1.251	1.855	.000	1.684	1.367	2.074	.000	
Richest		1	.	.	.	1	.	.	.	
Functional Difficulty										
Has	Functional	1.081	.810	1.443	.597	.956	.705	1.296	.771	
Difficulty										
Has	No Functional	1	.	.	.	1	.	.	.	
Difficulty										
Ethnicity										
Akan						1.602	.098	26.193	.741	
Ga/Damgme						2.029	.123	33.435	.621	

Ewe	1.872	.114	30.804	.661
Guan	1.818	.108	30.462	.678
Gruma	.833	.050	13.859	.899
Mole Dagbani	1.988	.122	32.494	.630
Grusi	1.427	.086	23.581	.804
Mande	.772	.039	15.350	.865
Other	1.387	.084	22.780	.819
No Response	1	.	.	.
Urban/Rural Residence				
Urban	.828	.695	.987	.036
Rural	1	.	.	.
Region				
Western	3.416	2.379	4.905	.000
Central	7.456	4.938	11.258	.000
Greater Accra	3.492	2.430	5.018	.000
Volta	4.178	2.742	6.366	.000
Eastern	2.845	1.977	4.094	.000
Ashanti	2.408	1.728	3.357	.000
Brong Ahafo	1.183	.846	1.655	.326
Northern	1.350	1.010	1.805	.043
Upper East	.748	.558	1.001	.051
Upper West	1	.	.	.

Note: OR= Odd Ratio, CI=95% Wald Confidence Interval for Exp (B), 1= Set to zero because this parameter is redundant.

Introducing the contextual or geo-related variables of ethnicity, area (rural/urban), and regional location generally improved the predictive abilities of the previous sociodemographic factors. Preceding that improvement, the parameters under ethnicity had higher odd ratios; however, none of the parameters under this construct had a significant p-value. Departing from ethnicity, rural/urban residence showed an odd ratio of 0.828 with a lower Wald interval of 0.695 and an upper Wald interval of 0.987 at a p-value of 0.036. Subsequently, most of the parameters under regional location had the highest odd ratio, with a region exhibiting an odd ratio of 7.456 with a lower bound of 4.938 and an upper bound of 11.258 at $p < 0.001$. Thus, the interplay of sociodemographic and geo-related factors accentuates the tendency of health insurance enrolment among men in this study.

DISCUSSION

The study explored the effects of selected compositional and contextual factors on men's health insurance coverage using data obtained through a nationally representative micro indicator cluster survey. The preliminary section of the results presented a descriptive analysis of the frequency and percentages of the measured items. The selection of age, education level, wealth index quintile, and marital status as key sociodemographic determinants of health insurance enrolment were supported by existing studies [1,6,8]. However, this study delves deeper into examining the influence of these variables on a mono-gender group, herein being men between the ages of 15 to 49 years.

The inclusion of functional difficulty among men as an independent variable in this study was to help ascertain the effect of the parameter as a critical instrument for achieving the inclusive and pro-poor objectives of Ghana's national health insurance scheme. Concerning the innate reasons behind the non-subscription to health insurance schemes, it was observed that high premium packages did not account for the significant reason. This can be attributed to the pluralistic sources of funding for the health insurance scheme, where the majority of the covered respondents had subscriptions, as indicated by 41.4% of the men surveyed. However, lack of money to register for insurance in private and public schemes constituted the main reason among 9.3% of the respondents, followed by the reasons for not requiring insurance. It can be deduced from the findings that the majority of the respondents knew of a health insurance scheme. However, lack of confidence in the scheme's operation, as signified by 1.5%, and the issue of far proximity to the registration office, as indicated by 2.1% of the total respondents surveyed, were cited as reasons for never registering for health insurance. By and large, the data obtained from the reasons did not account for the considerable gap between the currently enrolled respondents, who are 40.9%, and non-enrolled respondents, who are 59.1%. Hence, there is a need for an extensive examination of the sociodemographic and context-specific underpinning factors behind health insurance coverage among men.

Spearman's rho correlation analysis revealed a positive relationship between age and health insurance coverage and a similar relationship between rural/urban residence and health insurance coverage. These findings are consistent with the findings of several authors [1,10,11], who found a similar relationship between these demographic and contextual factors and health insurance enrolment within general demographics.

Subsequently, establishing two multivariable ordinal logistic regression models testing the effects of the sociodemographic variables in one dimension and proceeding to compound the sociodemographic and contextual variables in the second model led to observing significant predictive impacts of some of the constructs. At 95% confidence intervals, it was observed that educational level and wealth index quintile were the most important predictors of health insurance coverage among men in Model 1, as signified by an odd ratio of 3.914, 95% CI, 2.931 – 5.227; $p = 0.000$, and odd ratio of 1.879; 95% CI, 1.502 – 2.350; $p = 0.000$ for education level and wealth index respectively. This implies that while other variables in the model are held constant, higher education or wealth will increase the odds of men having health insurance coverage in Ghana.

Further, the addition of ethnicity, rural/urban area of residence, and regional location as contextual factors in model 2 revealed an improved effect of the existing sociodemographic variables except for functional difficulty, which was still insignificant. The insignificance of functional difficulty may be attributed to existing national policies that target the exemption of vulnerable groups from paying for national health insurance schemes and programs such as the Livelihood Empowerment Against Poverty (LEAP) [9,12,13]. More importantly, it was ascertained that ethnicity was not a significant predictor of health insurance coverage in the study. Mainly seen as a social solidarity and a tool for national and political cohesion, the national health insurance scheme, which the respondents assert as the main health insurance subscribed in this study, does not adversely select voluntary subscribers based on ethnic affiliation and hence the observance of these results.

The findings also showed that rural-urban residence significantly predicts health insurance coverage among men in this study. Urbanization can create access to healthcare facilities while enhancing proximity and reducing travel time to obtain health insurance registration and services. Finally, most of the parameters under region demonstrate that the regional construct was a significant predictor of health insurance coverage among men. The variations in regional levels of development and disparities in healthcare resources could account for the greater odd ratios and non-statically significant values observed in a few regions.

Study limitation

The study acknowledges the significance of gender equity and social inclusion considerations in research. However, this paper predominantly focuses on the relatively low health insurance enrollment of men in Ghana and within the context of most developing countries. The reasonably significant low health insurance enrolment among men, coupled with deep-seated adverse socio-cultural norms, may have spiral effects on health outcomes among men and other demographic groups. Hence, there is a need for considerable health marketing and financing strategies in research, segmentation, and targeting efforts to advance the discourse on individual, household, and communal level health insurance policies.

CONCLUSIONS

The study explored the relationship between selected compositional and contextual attributes and health insurance enrolment among men while not overlooking the perceived reasons for never subscribing to health insurance coverage. While acknowledging the relative dominance of men in communal and household decision-making as a result of deeply entrenched patriarchy and power dynamics in the study context, patterns of low health insurance coverage among the respondents revealed levels of vulnerabilities and gendered tendencies associated with enrolment in health insurance service. Though all men were interviewed in this study, variances in sociodemographic and context-specific factors led to differential effects in men's health insurance coverage. As developing countries strive to achieve universal health coverage for the greater population, it is crucial to consider segmentation and targeting of diverse population groups at the micro level and critically examine sociodemographic and locational dynamics that can influence acceptance and subscription to ex-ante coping mechanisms that can mitigate the financial burden associated with healthcare cost and at the same time enhance strategies put forward to promote universal healthcare coverage. Thus, efforts to improve health insurance coverage among men should focus on improving opportunities for general education, wealth, and residential equality in health insurance registration and healthcare delivery services.

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